

Supporting Information

For the article entitled: *A Framework for Computer-Aided Design and Manufacturing of Habitat Structures for Cavity-Dependent Animals*

This Supporting Information document provides background on the case-study project which designed, manufactured, and deployed artificial cavities for the powerful owl (*Ninox strenua*). It provides (a) information on the stakeholder engagement, (b) a summary of the case-study, and (c) details of the design workflow.

A. Stakeholder Engagement

Table S1 summarises our engagement with stakeholders and what we learned about their preferences for artificial-cavity designs. Meetings with stakeholders affirmed our rationale for using computational tools to systematically integrate multiple preferences. We found that stakeholders were not very familiar with the proposed methods but saw their potential and encouraged experimentation. We also found it particularly worthwhile to consider the preferences of nonhuman stakeholders (i.e., owls) in relation to human stakeholders. All human stakeholders continue to collaborate with the project and have expressed interest in supporting further research and implementation. All human stakeholders shared the goal of providing habitat structures for animals. Further research will invite other participants, such as community members, who may or may not share these objectives. Our stakeholder engagement confirmed that broad participation and the integration of multiple knowledges strengthens habitat-creation initiatives.

Table S1: Stakeholder consultation.

Stakeholder	[Type of Engagement] Stakeholder Role	Stakeholder Preferences
Owls	[Observation; Review of literature] Target species; potential user of habitat interventions	Place cavities within tree canopy, at appropriate heights, and in areas that have suitable climates, prey, and structures for roosting, foraging, and fledging Accommodate room for parents and 1–2 young, with sufficient cavity size and entrance width Match functional properties of usual nesting sites, including rough areas to scratch, climb, and feed Use materials and geometries that are non-toxic, drainable, thermally stable, biodegradable, and durable/long-lasting (as pairs may return to same nest for many years if nesting is successful) Facilitate usual behaviour of owls during the breeding season in winter, where the breeding pair visits the nest tree for several weeks before laying eggs, the male prepares the nest by racking up debris on cavity floor (and often does not return inside), the female lays eggs in May/June, and incubates the eggs until young fledge in July-October (Higgins, 1990) Support the prey base of owls
Scientists (2 owl ecology experts and 2 urban ecologists)	[Interviews; Informal storytelling; Fieldtrips]	Provide desirable habitat for the owls Meet ethics regulations Support target species

	<p>Provide insights into physiology and behaviours of target species, with consideration of non-target species</p> <p>Provide insights into the characteristics of owl habitat such as nests</p> <p>Help locate appropriate installation sites</p> <p>Guide owl observation fieldtrips</p> <p>Guide data collection methods, monitoring procedures, and ethical practices</p>	Function within ecosystem without too much disturbance
Arborists (5 tree climbers)	<p>[<i>Meetings; Informal storytelling; Fieldtrips</i>]</p> <p>Ensure safe installation and use of materials</p> <p>Provide anecdotal evidence of local species populations and behaviour</p> <p>Advise on best practices for nest placement and installation</p>	<p>Support quick and easy installation, e.g., through use of lightweight materials, inclusion of multiple fixing points, and installation at crotch junctions</p> <p>Meet safety regulations by avoiding organic-based or unrated fixing materials e.g., use yale brace for securing the nest to the tree</p> <p>Ensure habitat structure and its fixings are not harmful to the host-tree</p>
Land managers (3 local government representatives, 3 university grounds staff, and a biodiversity coordinator)	<p>[<i>Meetings; Consultations</i>]</p> <p>Help locate appropriate installation sites</p> <p>Provide insights into the local land-management practices and plans</p>	<p>Use/develop affordable materials and designs</p> <p>Foster community engagement</p> <p>Ensure habitat designs are scalable and repeatable</p>
Community members	[<i>Not formally engaged</i>]	<p>Attempt to make habitat designs aesthetically acceptable</p> <p>Support more species and therefore more sightings, without creating interspecies conflict</p>
Engineers (1 academic/engineer)	<p>[<i>Meetings; Consultations</i>]</p> <p>Advise on structural systems and safety measures to ensure arborists regulations are met</p>	Ensure safe, secure, and long-lasting installations
Designers	<p>[<i>Ongoing consultation with stakeholders; Collaborative design development</i>]</p> <p>Lead the material selection, fixing methods, geometries and sizes, aesthetics, and construction techniques</p>	<p>Integrate the multiple knowledges and preferences of stakeholders into habitat design</p> <p>Enhance the quality of habitats</p>
All stakeholders	<p>[<i>Workshops for design presentation and feedback</i>]</p> <p>Provide feedback on the suitability of proposed design elements</p>	Establish novel and suitable methods for designing, manufacturing, and deploying habitat structures

B. Summary of Case-Study

Table S2 provides additional details on the design, manufacturing, and deployment of each cavity in the case-study project. It includes details on the sizes, materials, manufacturers, software, and suppliers. This table lays out a clear comparison between approaches and allows others to make use of the relevant aspects of our approach.

Table S2: Specifications and comparative outcomes of deployed cavities.

	Nest Box	Carved Log	3D-Printed Wood Cavity	Hempcrete Cavity
Design				

Overall size	4-500 x 4-500 x 7-800mm	~1300 x 700 x 700mm	500 x 435 x 805mm (excluding entrance)	550 x 475 x 725mm (excluding entrance)
Entrance width	Min. 200mm	~200mm	150–200mm	150–200mm
Software	N/A	N/A	CloudCompare for processing 3D scans; Rhinoceros 3D and Grasshopper 3D for design and modelling	CloudCompare for processing 3D scans; Rhinoceros 3D and Grasshopper 3D for design and modelling
Manufacturing				
Manufacturing approaches	Conventional manufacturing	Chainsaw-carving	Computer-aided manufacturing (using Makerbot's Replicator+ 3D printer)	Computer-aided manufacturing (using CNC cutting at Lohas)
Manufacturers	N/A	N/A	NextLab, using ColorFabb's WoodFill filament in Makerbot's Replicator+ 3D printer	Lohas produced and CNC-cut Wood Wool Cement Board; Hemp Building Company supplied hempcrete mixture
Assemblers	Jim Greenwood	Melbourne Tree Care	First author, using Microsoft HoloLens augmented reality headset and Fologram software	First author, using Microsoft HoloLens augmented reality headset and Fologram software
Wall thickness	18mm	variable	25–50mm	30–60mm
Materials	Plywood	Natural log (either felled or fallen)	Minimum 30% recycled wood and a plant-based polylactide (commonly known as PLA) plastic	Hempcrete (1 part hemp, 2 parts lime, 4 parts water and 1 part sand) and wood-cement (FSC certified wood fibre, Portland cement, and water)
Fixing materials	Steel chain	Steel bar, yale brace	Knotted meshwork (3mm UV-resistant braided rope with CE-certification rated to 250kg)	Knotted meshwork (3mm UV-resistant braided rope with CE-certification rated to 300kg)
Time to manufacture	0.5 days	1 day	45 days on 1 printer	5 days
Time to assemble	0.25 days	0.5 days	1 day	2 days
Weight	20kg	250+kg	15kg	40kg
Deployment				
Cost including materials, installation, labour, sensors and holders (in brackets: cost for materials only)	\$800 (\$300-400)	\$1550 (\$525)	\$2850 (\$1050)	\$2250 (\$450)
Installation approaches	Pulley system: 1 person on ground, 1 in tree	Pulley system using trucks to hoist: 2 persons on ground, 1 in tree	Pulley system: 1 person on ground, 1 in tree	Pulley system: 1 person on ground, 1 in tree
Number of cavities	2	2	1	2
Installation sites	Ferntree Gully The Basin	Ferntree Gully The Basin	Parkville	Ferntree Gully The Basin
Host-tree type	Manna Gum (<i>Eucalyptus viminalis</i>)	Manna Gum (<i>Eucalyptus viminalis</i>)	Sydney Blue Gum (<i>Eucalyptus saligna</i>)	Manna Gum (<i>Eucalyptus viminalis</i>)

	Swamp Gum (<i>Eucalyptus ovata</i>)	Swamp Gum (<i>Eucalyptus ovata</i>)		Swamp Gum (<i>Eucalyptus ovata</i>)
Time to install	0.2 days	0.3 days	0.1 days	0.1 days
Offsite microclimate range over 4 days in winter (June)	Range: 4.3–27.5°C Average: 12.2°C	Range: 8.3–14.9°C Average: 11.2°C	Not tested	Range: 6.6–18.5°C Average: 10.4°C
Onsite microclimate range over 6 months from winter (July) to summer (January)	Range: 0.5–42°C Average: 14.7°C	Range: 4.5–33°C Average: 14.3°C	Range: 2.5–42.5°C Average: 15.4°C	Range: 2–37.5°C Average: 13.7°C
Species uptake (in brackets: species that used cavities)		Crimson rosella (<i>Platycercus elegans</i>); Galah (<i>Eolophus roseicapilla</i>)	Common ringtail possum (<i>Pseudocheirus peregrinus</i>); Rainbow lorikeet (<i>Trichoglossus moluccanus</i>)	Rainbow lorikeet (<i>Trichoglossus moluccanus</i>)

C. Details of the Design Workflow

The following images provide a step-by-step outline of the design workflow for producing computationally designed cavities. This guide comments on a Grasshopper 3D definition (refer to File 1) that we also include. This recipe allows others to reproduce the design, manufacturing, and deployment phases of the case-study. The workflow is applicable to other sites and species. We support each step with images that show the workflow’s capacity for experimentation and additional details that provide background on the design decisions we made for owls alongside possible alternatives.

Figure S1. Creating and deforming the cavity's base-geometry. This process uses Ken Perlin's simplex noise algorithms to generate the variety of undulations in the computationally designed cavities (top left). It then adjusts the cavity size and proportions to suit different species (top right). Figure in support of Section 3.1.1 Create Geometry Using Generative Design.

Figure S2. Adding and adjusting the entrance then subtracting the host-structure from the cavity. This process can adjust the geometry, length, angle, and number of entrances (top left). Using Boolean processes, the custom fit to the host site also works on any 3D scanned mesh (right) (refer to Figure S7). Figure in support of Section 3.1.2 Adjust Geometry Using Parametric Modelling.

Figure S3. Subdividing the cavity into modules for manufacturing using voxelization (left). This step can also use alternative geometries such as dodecahedrons (bottom). Smooth and non-modular options are also available (right). Figure in support of Section 3.1.2 Adjust Geometry Using Parametric Modelling.

Figure S4. Modelling the knotted harness. This step offers multiple types of harnesses (top) at multiple densities (bottom). Figure in support of Section 3.1.2 Adjust Geometry Using Parametric Modelling.

Figure S5. 3D printing the cavity components. 3D printers support multiple materials (e.g., wood and clay), geometries (left), internal patterns, densities, and thicknesses (right). The printing software allows for adjustment, fine-tuning, and repeatability (refer to Files 2.0–2.1). Figure in support of Section 3.2.1 Make Components Using 3D Printing.

Figure S6. Optimising the cavity components for assembly. This process groups voxels together to half the number of modules needed to assemble and distribute modules of different functions into suitable locations (i.e., porous drainage modules toward the base) (top right). It then slices the cavity into sections (top) that project onto the assembler's augmented-reality goggles to guide assembly (bottom). Figure in support of Section 3.2.2 Assemble Components Using Augmented Reality.

Figure S7. Processing the 3D-scanned point clouds of the host-structure (left) and locating the attachment site (right). Figure in support of Section 3.3.1 Install Prototypes Using 3D Scanning.

Figure S8. Construction documentation of a computationally designed cavity installation as reviewed by a structural engineer. Figure in support of Section 3.3.1 Install Prototypes Using 3D Scanning.

Figure S9. Assessing the microclimate performance of the cavities using data loggers that record temperature and humidity. We designed and 3D printed a custom data-logger holder (top right) that is smaller, less intrusive, and easier to reproduce than existing data-logger holders (top left, photography from Birdlife Australia) (refer to Files 3.0–3.1). Testing offsite provides data to ensure the cavity designs are not too hot for inhabitants. Testing onsite provides data on species use and microclimate that can feed back into the cavity designs (middle, right, and following images). Figure in support of Section 3.3.2 Manage Prototypes Using Data-Driven Design.

Figure S10. Wide-ranging potential of computationally designed cavities. Generative design processes support the production and testing of many, often unexpected, design options. These techniques support exploration which can help develop, test, or fine-tune affordances of designs that suit different target species (bottom). They also have the capacity to integrate numerical data that represent abiotic factors such as wind, gravity, humidity, or solar exposure (top) to iteratively develop a variety of performance-oriented geometries. Figure in support of Section 3.3.2 Manage Prototypes Using Data-Driven Design.

The following files allow others to view and edit the workflow above. All files are publicly available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5800162>

File 1.0. Grasshopper 3D Definition for Producing Computationally Designed Cavities: This file provides the Grasshopper 3D definition we used in the creation and adjustment of cavity geometries, inform the making and assembly of cavity components, and guide the installation and iterative development of cavity prototypes. It comes loaded with a sample 3D scanned host-tree but others may use their own.

Files 2.0–2.1. Modules for 3D Printing: This stereolithography file (2.0) provides the modules we used to assemble the computationally designed cavities. The corresponding print file (2.1) comes with the settings we used for 3D printing the wood filament.

Files 3.0–3.1. Data-Logger Holder for 3D Printing: This stereolithography file (3.0) provides the design we used to contain the iButtons – others may use this file to print their own. The corresponding print file (3.1) comes with the settings we used for 3D printing PLA filament.

Most entry level laptops or computers running Windows 10 should be adequate to view the supporting files. Software required: Rhinoceros 3D and Grasshopper 3D to load the processed 3D scan and to run the algorithm for the cavity designs. Grasshopper Plug-ins required: [4D Noise](#) (Giulio Piacentino), [Volvox](#) (Center for Information Technology and Architecture), [Weaverbird](#) (Giulio Piacentino), [Pufferfish](#) (Michael Pryor), [Nursery](#) (Gwyllim Jahn), Stinkbug (Alex Holland, unreleased), [Lunchbox](#) (Nathan Miller), and [Ladybug](#) (Ladybug Tools). Hardware required: 3D printer to print modules and iButton holder (MakerBot's Replicator+ with MakerBot Print Software, version 4.10.1.2056), and Microsoft Hololens with [Fologram](#) (Cameron Newnham, Nick van den Berg, and Gwyllim Jahn) for assembly.